

1 **ShellChron 0.4.0: A new tool for constructing chronologies in accretionary carbonate archives**
2 **from stable oxygen isotope profiles**

3 Niels J. de Winter^{1,2}

4 ¹Department of Earth Sciences, Utrecht University, Utrecht, the Netherlands

5 ²AMGC research group, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels, Belgium

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7 Corresponding author: Niels J de Winter (n.j.dewinter@uu.nl)

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11 **Abstract**

12 This work presents ShellChron, a new model for generating accurate internal age models for high-
13 resolution paleoclimate archives, such as corals, mollusk shells and speleothems. Reliable sub-annual
14 age models form the backbone of high-resolution paleoclimate studies. In absence of independent sub-
15 annual growth markers in many of these archives, the most reliable method for determining the age of
16 samples is through age modelling based on stable oxygen isotope or other seasonally controlled proxy
17 records. ShellChron expands on previous solutions to the age model problem by fitting a combination
18 of a growth rate and temperature sinusoid to model seasonal variability in the proxy record in a sliding
19 window approach. This new approach creates smoother, more precise age-distance relationships for
20 multi-annual proxy records with the added benefit of allowing assessment of the uncertainty on the
21 modelled age. The modular script of ShellChron allows the model to be tailored to specific archives,
22 without being limited to oxygen isotope proxy records or carbonate archives, with high flexibility in
23 assigning the relationship between the input proxy and the seasonal cycle. The performance of
24 ShellChron in terms of accuracy and computation time is tested on a set of virtual seasonality records
25 and real coral, mollusk and speleothem archives. The result shows that several key improvements in
26 comparison to previous age model routines enhance the accuracy of ShellChron on multi-annual records
27 while limiting its processing time. The current full working version of ShellChron enables the user to

28 model the age of a 10-year long high-resolution (16 samples/yr) carbonate records with monthly
29 accuracy within one hour of computation time on a personal computer. The model is freely accessible
30 on the CRAN database and GitHub. Members of the community are invited to contribute by adapting
31 the model code to suit their research topics and encouraged to cite the original work of Judd et al. (2018)
32 alongside this work when using ShellChron in future studies.

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35 **1. Introduction**

36 Fast growing carbonate archives, such as coral skeletons, mollusk shells and speleothems, contain a
37 wealth of information about past and present climate and environment (e.g. Urban et al., 2000; Wang et
38 al., 2001; Steuber et al., 2005; Butler et al., 2013). Recent advances in analytical techniques have
39 improved our ability to extract this information and obtain records of the conditions under which these
40 carbonates precipitated at high temporal resolutions, often beyond the annual scale (Treble et al., 2007;
41 Saenger et al., 2017; Vansteenberge et al., 2019; de Winter et al., 2020a; Ivany and Judd, 2022). Key
42 to the interpretation of such records is the development of reliable chemical or physical proxies for
43 climate and environmental conditions which can be measured on a sufficiently fine scale to allow
44 variability to be reconstructed at the desired time resolution. Examples of suitable proxies include
45 observations of variability in carbonate fabric and microstructure and in (trace) elemental and isotopic
46 composition (Frisia et al., 2000; Lough, 2010; Ullmann et al., 2010; Schöne et al., 2011; Ullmann et al.,
47 2013; Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014; de Winter et al., 2017). The unique preservation potential of
48 carbonates in comparison with archives of climate variability at similar time resolutions, such as tree ring
49 records and ice cores, now allows us to recover information about climate and environment of the
50 geological past from these proxies on the (sub-)seasonal scale (Ivany and Runnegar, 2010; Ullmann
51 and Korte, 2015; Vansteenberge et al., 2016; de Winter et al., 2018; 2020b; c; Mohr et al., 2020). The
52 importance of this development cannot be overstated because variability at high (daily and seasonal)
53 resolution constitutes the most significant component of climate variability (Mitchell, 1976; Huybers and
54 Curry, 2006; Zhu et al., 2019; von der Heydt et al., 2021). Accurate reconstructions of this type of
55 variability are therefore fundamental to our understanding of Earth's climate system and critical for
56 projecting its behavior in the future under anthropogenic global warming conditions (IPCC, 2021).

57 A reliable age model is crucial for the interpretation of high-resolution carbonate records. An age model
58 is defined as a set of rules or markers that allows the translation of the location of a measurement or
59 observation on the archive to the time at which the carbonate was precipitated. This translation is
60 required for aligning records from multiple proxies or archives on a common time axis. Age alignment
61 enables data to be intercomparable and to be interpreted in the context of processes playing a role at
62 similar timescales. Age models are based on knowledge about the growth or accretion rate of the archive
63 through time. Many high-resolution carbonate archives contain growth markers on which age models
64 can be based (e.g. Jones, 1983; Le Tissier et al., 1994; Verheyden et al., 2006). These are especially
65 valuable in some mollusk species, in which growth lines demarcate annual, daily, or even tidal cycles
66 (e.g. *Arctica islandica*, Schöne et al., 2005; *Pecten maximus*, Chavaud et al., 2005 and *Cerastoderma*
67 *edule*, Mahé et al., 2010). However, in many mollusk species and most carbonate archives, such
68 independent growth indicators are absent or too infrequent to (relatively) date high-resolution
69 measurements (Judd et al., 2018; Huyghe et al., 2019). In such cases, age models need to be based
70 on alternative indicators.

71 The oxygen isotope composition of carbonates ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$) is closely dependent on the isotopic composition
72 of the fluid ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) and the temperature at which the carbonate is precipitated (Urey, 1948; McCrea,
73 1950; Epstein et al., 1953). In most natural surface environments, either one or both factors is strongly
74 dependent on the seasonal cycle, one generally being dominant over the other. This causes carbonates
75 precipitated in these environments to display strong quasi-sinusoidal variations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ that record the
76 seasonal cycle (e.g. Dunbar and Wellington, 1981; Jones and Quitmyer, 1996; Baldini et al., 2008).
77 Examples of this behavior include seasonal cyclicity in sea surface temperatures recorded in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
78 of corals and mollusks and seasonal cyclicity in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ of precipitation recorded in speleothems
79 (Dunbar and Wellington, 1981; Schöne et al., 2005; Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014). This relationship is
80 challenged in tropical latitudes, where temperature seasonality is restricted. However, in some tropical
81 archives, the annual cycle of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ in precipitation still allows the annual cycle to be resolved from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
82 records (e.g. Evans and Schrag, 2004). These properties make $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ one of the most highly sought-
83 after proxies for climate variability, and high-resolution $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records are abundant in the paleoclimate
84 literature (e.g. Lachniet, 2009; Lough, 2010; Schöne and Gillikin, 2013 and references therein).

85 The close relationship between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records and the seasonal cycle can also be exploited to estimate
86 variability in growth rate of the archive. This property of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curves has been recognized by previous

87 authors, and attempts have been made to quantify intra-annual growth rates from the shape of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
88 profiles (Wilkinson and Ivany, 2002; Goodwin et al., 2003; De Ridder et al., 2006; Goodwin et al., 2009;
89 De Brauwere et al., 2009; Müller et al., 2015; Judd et al., 2018). Over time, these so called “growth
90 models” have improved from fitting of sinusoids to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data (Wilkinson and Ivany, 2002; De Ridder et
91 al., 2006) to including increasingly complicated (inter)annual growth rate curves to the model to fit the
92 shape of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data (Goodwin et al., 2003; 2009; Müller et al., 2015; Judd et al., 2018). These later
93 models manage to fit the shape of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records well, but they often rely on detailed *a priori* knowledge
94 of growth rate or temperature patterns (e.g. Goodwin et al., 2003; 2009), which requires measurements
95 of one or more parameters in the environment. These measurements are not available in studies on
96 carbonate archives from the archeological or geological past. In contrast, the latest model by Judd et al.
97 (2018; GRATAISS, or “Growth Rate and Temporal Alignment of Isotopic Serial Samples”) is based only
98 on the assumption that growth and temperature follow quasi-sinusoidal patterns and can therefore work
99 with $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data alone, making it more widely applicable. The simplified parameterization of temperature
100 and growth rate seasonality by Judd et al. (2018) using two (skewed) sinusoids is demonstrated to
101 approximate natural circumstances very well.

102 However, the GRATAISS model is still limited in its use because it requires whole, individual growth
103 years to be analyzed separately, resulting in a discontinuous time series when applied on records
104 containing multiple years of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data and no solution for incomplete years. In addition, the model has
105 no option to supply information about the less dominant factor that drives $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ of sea
106 water in the case of mollusks and corals). Furthermore, only estimates from aragonite records are
107 supported, while the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ value of the other dominant carbonate mineral, calcite, has a different
108 temperature relationship (Kim and O’Neil, 1997). Finally, neither of the models highlighted above except
109 for the MoGroFun model by Goodwin et al. (2009) include any assessment of the uncertainty of the
110 constructed age model.

111 Here, a new model for estimating ages of samples in seasonal $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curves is presented which
112 combines the advantages of previous models while attempting to negate their disadvantages.
113 ShellChron combines a skewed growth rate sinusoid with a sinusoidal temperature curve to model $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
114 using the Shuffled Complex Evolution model developed at the University of Arizona (SCEUA; Duan et
115 al., 1992; following Judd et al., 2018). It applies this optimization using a sliding window through the
116 dataset (as in Wilkinson and Ivany, 2002) and includes the option to use a Monte Carlo simulation

117 approach to combine uncertainties on the input ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ and sample distance measurements) and the
 118 model routine (as in Goodwin et al., 2009). As a result, ShellChron produces a continuous time series
 119 with a confidence envelope, supports records from multiple carbonate minerals and allows the user to
 120 provide information on the less dominant variable influencing $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ (e.g. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) if available (see **section**
 121 **2**). The modular design of ShellChron's functional script allows parts of the model to be adapted and
 122 interchanged, supporting a wide range of climate and environmental archives. As a result, the initial
 123 design of ShellChron for reconstructing age models in temperature-dominated $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records from
 124 marine bio-archives (e.g. corals and mollusks) presented here can be easily modified for application on
 125 other types of records. The routine is worked out into a ready-to-use package for the open-source
 126 computational programming language R and is directly available without restrictions, allowing all
 127 interested parties to freely modify and build on the base structure to adapt it to their needs (R Core
 128 Team, 2020; full package code and documentation in **S11**, see also **Code availability**).

129

130 **2. Scientific basis**

131 The relationship between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ and the temperature of carbonate precipitation was first established by
 132 Urey (1951) and later refined with additional measurements and theoretical models (e.g. Epstein et al.,
 133 1953; Tarutani et al., 1969; Grossman and Ku, 1986; Kim and O'Neil, 1997; Coplen, 2007; Watkins et
 134 al., 2014; Daëron et al., 2019). Empirical transfer functions for aragonite and calcite by Grossmann and
 135 Ku (1986; modified by Dettmann et al., 1999; **equation 1**) and Kim and O'Neil (1997; **equation 2**, with
 136 VSMOW to VPDB scale conversion following Brand et al., 2014; **equation 3**) have so far found most
 137 frequent use in modern paleoclimate studies and are therefore applied as default relationships in the
 138 ShellChron model (see *d18O_model* function).

$$139 \quad T[^\circ\text{C}] = 20.6 - 4.34 * (\delta^{18}\text{O}_c[\text{‰VPDB}] - \delta^{18}\text{O}_w[\text{‰VSMOW}] + 0.2) \quad (1)$$

$$140 \quad 1000 * \ln(\alpha) = 18.03 * \frac{10^3}{(T[^\circ\text{C}] + 273.15)} - 32.42$$

$$141 \quad \text{with } \alpha = \frac{\left(\frac{\delta^{18}\text{O}_c[\text{‰VPDB}]}{1000} + 1\right)}{\left(\frac{\delta^{18}\text{O}_w[\text{‰VPDB}]}{1000} + 1\right)} \quad (2)$$

$$142 \quad \delta^{18}\text{O}_w[\text{‰VPDB}] = 0.97002 * \delta^{18}\text{O}_w[\text{‰VSMOW}] - 29.98 \quad (3)$$

143 To apply these formulae, it is assumed that carbonate is precipitated in equilibrium with the precipitation
144 fluid. Which carbonates are precipitated in equilibrium has long been subject to debate, and the
145 development of new techniques for measuring the carbonate-water system (e.g. clumped and dual-
146 clumped isotope analyses; Daëron et al., 2019; Bajnai et al., 2020) has led some authors to challenge
147 the assumption that equilibrium fractionation is the norm (see **Supplementary Discussion**). The
148 modular character of ShellChron allows the empirical transfer function to be adapted to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record
149 or to the user's preference for alternative transfer functions by a small modification of the *d18O_model*
150 function. Future versions of the model will include more options for changing the transfer function (see
151 **Model description**).

152 As the name suggests, the ShellChron model was initially developed for application on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records
153 from marine calcifiers (e.g. mollusk shells and corals). ShellChron approximates the evolution of the
154 calcification temperature at which the carbonate is precipitated by a sinusoidal function (see **equation**
155 **4, Table 1** and **SI4**; *temperature_curve* function; visualized in **Fig. 4A** and **Fig S1**), a good approximation
156 of seasonal temperature fluctuations in most marine and terrestrial environments (Wilkinson and Ivany,
157 2002; Ivany and Judd, 2022). Variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ is also comparatively limited in most marine
158 environments (except for regions with sea ice formation), making the model easy to use in these settings
159 (LeGrande and Schmidt, 2006; Rohling, 2013). Nevertheless, ShellChron includes the option to provide
160 *a priori* knowledge about $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, ranging from annual average values to detailed seasonal variability,
161 enabling the model to work in environments with more complex interaction between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and
162 temperature on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record (see **equations 1 and 2**). This $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ data can be provided either as a
163 vector (with the same length as the data) or a single value (assuming constant $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) through the *d18Ow*
164 parameter in the *run_model* function.

$$165 \quad T[^\circ\text{C}] = T_{av} + \frac{T_{amp}}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi * \left(t[d] - T_{pha} + \frac{T_{per}}{4}\right)}{T_{per}}\right) \quad (4)$$

166 If marine $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records represent one extreme on the spectrum of temperature versus $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ influence
167 on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record, cave environments, in which $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variability is predominantly driven by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$
168 variability in the precipitation fluid, represent the other extreme (Van Rangelbergh et al., 2014). In its
169 current form, ShellChron takes $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ as a user-supplied parameter to model temperature and growth
170 rate variability, but future versions will allow temperature to be fixed, while $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ becomes the modelled

171 variable. ShellChron's modular character makes it possible to implement this update without changing
 172 the structure of the model. Application of ShellChron on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records from cave deposits will have to
 173 be treated with caution, since drip water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ seasonality (if present) cannot always be approximated
 174 by a sinusoidal function and equilibrium fractionation in cave deposits is less common than in bio-
 175 archives (Baldini et al., 2008; Daëron et al., 2011; Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014).

176 Besides temperature (or $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) seasonality, ShellChron models the growth rate of the archive to
 177 approximate the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record (see **equation 5**, **Table 1** and **SI4**; *growth_rate_curve* function; visualized
 178 in **Fig. 4B** and **Fig S2**). Since the growth rate in many carbonate archives varies seasonally, a quasi-
 179 sinusoidal model for growth rate seems plausible (e.g. Le Tissier et al., 1994; Baldini et al., 2008; Judd
 180 et al., 2018). However, as discussed in Judd et al. (2018), the occurrence of growth cessations (growth
 181 rate = 0) and skewness in seasonal growth patterns calls for a more complex growth rate model that
 182 can take these properties into account. Therefore, ShellChron uses a slightly modified version of the
 183 skewed sinusoidal growth function described by Judd et al. (2018; **equation 5**). Note that the added
 184 complexity of this function does not preclude the modelling of growth rate functions described by a
 185 simple sinusoid (no skewness; $G_{skw} = 50$) or even constant growth through the year ($G_{amp} = 0$; see **Table**
 186 **1**).

$$187 \quad G[\text{mm/yr}] = G_{av} + \frac{G_{amp}}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi * (t[d] - G_{pha} + G_{per} * S)}{P}\right)$$

$$188 \quad \text{with } S = \begin{cases} \frac{100 - G_{skw}}{50}, & \text{if } t[d] - G_{pha} < G_{per} \frac{100 - G_{skw}}{100} \\ \frac{G_{skw}}{50}, & \text{if } t[d] - G_{pha} \geq G_{per} \frac{100 - G_{skw}}{100} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

189 Contrary to previous $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ growth models, ShellChron allows uncertainties on the input variables
 190 (sampling distance and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ measurements) as well as uncertainties of the full modelling approach to
 191 be propagated, providing confidence envelopes around the chronology. Uncertainty propagation is
 192 optional and can be skipped without compromising model accuracy. Standard deviations of uncertainties
 193 on input variables (sampling distance and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$) can be provided by the user, while model uncertainties
 194 are calculated from the variability in model results of the same datapoint obtained from overlapping
 195 simulation windows (see *growth_model* function). Measurement errors are combined by projecting
 196 Monte Carlo simulated values for sampling distance and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ measurements on the modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
 197 curve through an orthogonal projection (**equation 6**; *mc_err_orth* function; visualized in **Fig S3**). The

198 measurement uncertainty projected on the distance domain is then combined with the model uncertainty
 199 to obtain pooled uncertainties in the distance domain, which are propagated through the modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
 200 record to obtain uncertainties on the model result in the age domain. As a result of the sliding window
 201 approach in ShellChron, model results for datapoints situated at the edges of windows are more
 202 sensitive to small changes in the modelled parameters and therefore possess a larger model
 203 uncertainty. To prevent these least certain model estimates from affecting the stability of the model,
 204 model results are given more weight the closer they are situated towards the center of the model window
 205 (see **equation 7** in *export_results* function; see also **Fig. S4**). This weighting is also incorporated in
 206 uncertainty propagation through a weighted standard deviation (see **equation 8** from the *sd_wt*
 207 function). Note that, despite the weighting solution, the size of uncertainties on the first and last positions
 208 in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record remains uncertain since they are based on a smaller number of overlapping windows
 209 (see e.g. **Figure 3**).

$$210 \quad \sigma_{meas} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{D_{sim} - \bar{D}_{sim}}{\sigma_D}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta^{18}\text{O}_{sim} - \bar{\delta}^{18}\text{O}_{sim}}{\sigma_{\delta^{18}\text{O}}}\right)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$211 \quad w[i] = 1 - \left| \frac{2i}{L_{window}} - 1 \right| \quad (7)$$

$$212 \quad \sigma_{weighted,i} = \sqrt{\frac{w_i * (x_i - \bar{w})^2}{\sum w[i] * \frac{N-1}{N}}} \quad (8)$$

213

214 3. Model description

215 ShellChron is organized as a series of functions that describe the step-by-step modelling process. A
 216 schematic overview of the model is given in **Fig. 1**. A short **Test Case** is used to illustrate the modelling
 217 steps in ShellChron. **Fig. 2** shows how the virtual **Test Case** was created from randomly generated
 218 seasonal growth rate, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and temperature curves using the *seasonalclumped* R package (de Winter
 219 et al., 2021a; see **Fig. 2, Supplementary Methods** and **S12**) A wrapper function (*wrap_function*) is
 220 included, which carries out all steps of the model procedure in succession to promote ease of use.

221 Data is imported through the *data_import* function, which takes a comma-separated text file (CSV) with
 222 the input data. Data files need to contain columns containing sampling distance (D , in μm) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$

223 data (in ‰VPDB), a column marking years in the record (*yearmarkers*) and two optional columns
224 containing uncertainties on sampling distance ($\sigma(D)$, one standard deviation, in μm) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ ($\sigma(\delta^{18}\text{O}_c)$,
225 one standard deviation, in ‰) respectively (see example in **SI2** and **Figure 3**). The function uses the
226 year markers (third column) as guidelines for defining the minimum length of the model windows to
227 ensure that all windows contain at least one year of growth. By default, consecutive windows are shifted
228 by one datapoint, yielding a total number of windows equal to the sample size minus the length of the
229 last window. While year markers are required for ShellChron to run (otherwise no windows can be
230 defined), the result of the model does not otherwise depend on user-provided year markers, instead
231 basing the age result purely on simulations of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data.

232 The core of the model consists of simulations of overlapping subsamples (windows) of the sampling
233 distance and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data described by the *run_model* function (see **Fig. 1 and 3**). Data and window sizes
234 are passed from *data_import* onto *run_model* along with user-provided parameters (e.g. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$
235 information; see **Fig. 1**). *run_model* loops through the data windows and calls the *growth_model*
236 function, which fits a modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ vs. distance curve through the data using the SCEUA optimization
237 algorithm (see Duan et al., 1992; see example in **Fig 4**). The simulated $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve is produced through
238 a combination of a temperature sinusoid (*temperature_curve* function; see **equation 4, Fig. 4A and Fig.**
239 **S1**) and a skewed growth rate sinusoid (*growth_rate_curve*; see **equation 5, Fig. 4B and Fig. S2**), with
240 temperature data converted to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data through the *d18O_model* function (**equation 1 and 2; Fig.**
241 **4A**).

242 By default, starting values for the parameters describing temperature and growth rate curves are
243 obtained by estimating the annual period (P) through a spectral density estimation and applying a
244 linearized sinusoidal regression through the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data (*sinreg* function; see **equation 9**). It is possible
245 to skip this sinusoidal modelling step through the “*sinfit*” parameter in the *run_model* function, in which
246 case the starting value for the annual period is set equal to the width of the model window. In addition,
247 *growth_model* takes a series of parameters describing the method for SCEUA optimization (see Duan
248 et al., 1992; Judd et al., 2018) and the upper and lower bounds for parameters describing temperature
249 and growth rate curves (see **SI4**). Parameters for the SCEUA algorithm (*iniflg*, *ngs*, *maxn*, *kstop*, *pcento*
250 and *peps*) in the *run_model* function may be modified by the user to reach more desirable optimization
251 outcomes. The effect of changing the SCEUA parameters on the model result for the **Test case** is
252 illustrated in **section 4.1** (see **Fig. 5**). If uncertainties on sampling distance and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data are provided,

253 *growth_model* calls the *mc_err_orth* function to propagate these errors through the model result (see
 254 **equation 6** and **Fig S3**).

$$255 \quad \delta^{18}O_c[\text{‰VPDB}] = I + \frac{A}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi * \left(D - \varphi + \frac{P}{4}\right)}{P}\right),$$

$$256 \quad \text{linearized as: } \delta^{18}O_c[\text{‰VPDB}] = a + b \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{P} * D\right) + c \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{P} * D\right),$$

$$257 \quad \text{with } I = a; A = \sqrt{b^2 + c^2} \text{ and } \varphi = P * \left(0.25 - \frac{\cos^{-1}\left(\frac{b}{A}\right)}{2\pi}\right) \text{ (9)}$$

258 The *run_model* function returns an array listing day of the year (1–365), temperature, $\delta^{18}O_c$, growth rate
 259 and (optionally) their uncertainty standard deviations as propagated from uncertainties on the input data
 260 (“result array”; see **Fig. 3** and **S15**). Note that the default length of the year (*Tper* and *Gper*) is set at 365
 261 days, but that these parameters can be modified by the user in *run_model*. In addition, a matrix
 262 containing the optimized parameters of temperature and growth rate curves is provided, yielding
 263 information about the evolution of mean values, phases, amplitudes, and skewness of seasonality in
 264 temperature and growth rate along the record (“parameter matrix”, see **Fig. 1** and **S16**). To construct an
 265 age model for the entire record, the modelled timing of growth data, expressed as day relative to the
 266 365-day year, is converted into a cumulative time series listing the number of days relative to the start
 267 of the first year represented in the record (rather than relative to the start of the year in which the
 268 datapoint is found). This requires year transitions (transitions from day 365 to day 1) to be recognized
 269 in all the model results. The *cumulative_day* function achieves this by aggregating information about
 270 places where the beginning and end of the year is recorded in individual window simulations and
 271 applying a peak identification algorithm (*peakid* function) to find places in the record where year
 272 transitions occur (see **Supplementary Methods**). Results of the timing of growth for each sample (in
 273 day of the year) are converted to a cumulative time scale using their positions relative to these
 274 recognized year transitions (**Supplementary Methods**).

275 In a final step (described by the *export_results* function), the results from overlapping individual
 276 modelling windows are combined to obtain mean values and 95% confidence envelopes of the result
 277 variables (age, $\delta^{18}O_c$, $\delta^{18}O_c$ -based temperatures and growth rates) for each sample in the input data. If
 278 uncertainties on the input variables were provided, these are combined with uncertainties on the

279 modelling result calculated from results of the same datapoint on overlapping data windows by pooling
 280 the variance of the uncertainties (**equation 10**). Throughout this merging of data from overlapping
 281 windows, results from datapoints on the edge of windows are given less weight than those from
 282 datapoints near the center of a window (see **equation 7** and **Fig. S4**). This weighting procedure corrects
 283 for the fact that datapoints near the edge of a window are more susceptible to small changes in the
 284 model parameters and are therefore less reliable than results in the center of the window. Finally,
 285 summaries of the simulation results and the model parameters including their confidence intervals are
 286 exported as comma-separated (CSV) files. In addition, *export_results* supports optional exports of
 287 figures displaying the model results and files containing raw data of all individual model windows
 288 (equivalent to “sheets” of the result array, see **Fig. 3** and **SI5**).

$$289 \quad VAR_{pooled} = \frac{\sum_i((N_i-1)*VAR_i*w_i)}{\sum_i(N_i)-n} \quad (10)$$

290 in which w = weight of the individual reconstructions, N is the sample size and n is the number of
 291 reconstructions (indexed by i) that is combined

292

293 **4. Model performance**

294 The performance of ShellChron was first tested on three virtual datasets:

- 295 1. The short **Test case** used to illustrate the model steps above (see **Fig. 2** and **4; SI7**)
- 296 2. A $\delta^{18}O_c$ record constructed from a simulated temperature sinusoid with added stochastic noise
 297 (**Case 1; SI8**)
- 298 3. A record based on a known high-resolution sea surface temperature and salinity record
 299 measured on the coast of Texel island in the tidal basin of the Wadden Sea (North Netherlands;
 300 **Texel**, see details in **SI9** and de Winter et al., 2021a and **Supplementary Methods**).

301 Firstly, the effect of varying parameters in the SCEUA algorithm is tested on the **Test Case (Fig. 5)**.
 302 Then, full model runs on **Case 1** and **Texel** are evaluated in terms of model performance (**Fig. 6**). In
 303 addition to the three test cases, three modern carbonate $\delta^{18}O_c$ records were internally dated using
 304 ShellChron (see **Fig. 7**): a tropical stony coral (*Porites lutea*; hereafter: **coral**) from the Pandora Reef
 305 (Great barrier Reef, NE Australia; Gagan et al., 1993; see **SI10**), a Pacific oyster shell (*Crassostrea*
 306 *gigas*; hereafter: **oyster**) from List Basin in Denmark (Ullmann et al., 2010; see **SI10**) and a temperate

307 zone speleothem from Han-sur-Lesse cave (Belgium; hereafter: **speleothem**; see Vansteenberge et
308 al., 2019; see **SI10**). Finally, ShellChron's performance in terms of computation time and accuracy is
309 compared to that of the most comprehensive pre-existing $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -based age model (GRATAISS model
310 by Judd et al., 2018) on simulated temperature sinusoids of various length and sampling resolutions to
311 which stochastic noise was added (*sensu* **Case 1**; de Winter et al., 2021a; see **Fig. 8** and **SI11**). The
312 latter also demonstrates the scalability of ShellChron and its application on a variety of datasets. Timing
313 comparisons were carried out using a modern laptop (Dell XPS13–7390; Dell Inc., Round Rock, Tx,
314 USA) with an Intel Core i7 processor (8 MB cache, 4.1 GHz clock speed, 4 cores, Intel Corporation,
315 Santa Clara, CA, USA), 16 GB LPDDR3 RAM and an SSD drive running Windows 10. Note that
316 ShellChron was built and tested successfully on Mac OS, Fedora Linux and Ubuntu Linux as well.

317 **4.1 Testing model parameters**

318 Testing different combinations of modelling parameters (**Fig. 5**) shows that, while the results of
319 ShellChron can improve beyond the default SCEUA parameters and sinusoidal regression, care must
320 be taken to evaluate the effect of changing modelling parameters on both the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ fit and the age-
321 distance relationship. Comparative testing on the **Test case (Fig. 5)** shows that sinusoidal regression
322 has a negligible influence on the success of ShellChron fitting the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve (**Fig. 5A-B**; standard
323 deviation on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ is 0.49‰ with sinusoidal regression and 0.50‰ without). However, ShellChron with
324 sinusoidal regression performs better in terms of age approximation, with a mean age offset of only 7
325 \pm 32 days with sinusoidal regression against 32 \pm 35 days without (**Fig. 5C-D**). Age-distance plots
326 (**Fig. 5C**) show that the model without sinusoidal fit shows a phase offset with respect to the known
327 age-distance relationship, resulting in overestimation of the age for much of the record. Sinusoidal
328 regression probably results in better initial parameter estimation, which helps to avoid phase offsets
329 like the one shown in **Fig. 5**. For the remainder of the tests, sinusoidal regression was enabled.

330 The remainder of the tests show that the main bottleneck towards better $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ fit optimization is the
331 maximum number of function evaluations allowed within a single modelling cycle (maxn; see **Fig. 5**).
332 Increasing the other SCEUA parameters, such as the number of complexes in the SCEUA routine
333 (ngs), the number of shuffling loops that should show a significant change before convergence (kstop)
334 and the thresholds for significant change in parameter value (peps) or result value (pcento) does not
335 improve the result if the SCEUA algorithm is not allowed more processing time (maxn). In fact, **Fig. 5**

336 shows that increasing these SCEUA parameters can actually result in a deterioration of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ fit
337 and higher uncertainty on the age result (**Fig. 5B and D**). A fivefold increase in maxn ($\text{maxn} = 50000$)
338 almost halves the standard deviation on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ residuals (from 0.49‰ to 0.29‰; **Fig. 5B**) and
339 decreases the standard deviation on the age model offset from 32 to 26 days (**Fig. 5D**). A combination
340 of a tenfold increase in function evaluations with an equal multiplication of the number of complexes in
341 the SCEUA routine (ngs; see details in Duan et al., 1992) results in a further reduction of standard
342 deviations on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ (0.23‰) and age result (12 days). These tests show that returns in terms of model
343 precision quickly diminish with increasing processing time. Since the total modelling time linearly
344 scales with the number of function evaluations, this tradeoff towards lower standard deviation on the
345 modelling result is costly. These function evaluations are repeated in each modelling window, so the
346 cost in terms of extra processing time can increase quickly, especially for larger $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ datasets. In
347 addition, in this situation the mean model offset (accuracy of the model; 7 days, 28 days and 14 days
348 for maxn of $1.0 \cdot 10^4$, $5.0 \cdot 10^4$ and $1.0 \cdot 10^5$ respectively; **Fig. 5D**) does not significantly improve with
349 increasing number of function evaluations. Based on these results, the default maxn parameter in
350 ShellChron was set to 10^4 to compromise between keeping modelling times short while retaining high
351 model accuracy. However, specific datasets may benefit from an increase in modeling time, so case-
352 by-case assessment of the optimal SCEUA parameters is recommended. A detailed evaluation of the
353 total modelling time in a typical $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ dataset is discussed in **section 4.4**.

354

355 **4.2 Artificial carbonate records**

356 Results of running ShellChron on the **Test case (Fig. 4)**, **Case 1** and **Texel** datasets (**Fig. 6**) show that
357 modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records in individual windows closely match the data. On the level of individual windows,
358 inter-annual growth rate variability is more difficult to model than the temperature sinusoid, especially
359 when sampling resolution is limited and at the beginning and end of the record (**Fig. 4B**). However, after
360 overlapping multiple windows, the accuracy of ShellChron improves significantly (**Fig. 4E**). Note that in
361 **Fig. 4A-C**, the length of the first model window (difference in age between first and 11th datapoint) is
362 less than 365 days, because the 12th datapoint, which occurs exactly 1 year after the first point, is not
363 part of the window. A summary of ShellChron performance statistics is given in **Table 2**. In all virtual
364 datasets, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ estimates are equally distributed above and below the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data ($\overline{\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c} = 0.0 \text{ ‰}$;

365 Spearman's ρ of 0.94, 0.98 and 0.92 for **Test case**, **Case 1** and **Texel** datasets respectively). Age
366 offsets vary slightly over the seasons, but the difference between monthly time bins is not statistically
367 significant on a 95% confidence level (**Fig. 6C** and **F**; see also **SI12**). The fact that seasonal bias in age
368 offset is absent in the **Texel** dataset, which is skewed towards growth in the winter season and includes
369 relatively strong seasonal variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, shows that ShellChron is not sensitive to such subtle
370 (though common) variability in growth rate or $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$. In general, ShellChron's mean age assignment is
371 accurate on a monthly scale (age offsets of 4 ± 12 d and $+30 \pm 24$ d for **Case 1** and **Texel** datasets
372 respectively). However, age results in individual months do sometimes show significant offsets from the
373 known value (e.g. **Fig. 6C** and **6F**). This is most notable in **Case 1**, where accuracy of the age model
374 decreases near the extreme values of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve (**Fig. 6B-C**). This occurs because in these places
375 the model is most sensitive to stochastic noise (simulated uncertainty) on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ value. A small
376 random change in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ value at the minima or maxima of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve thus results in a large
377 change in the model fit of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve, resulting in a seasonally non-uniform decrease in the accuracy
378 of the model, as is evident from the skewed $\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ distribution in **Figure 6B-C**. The sampling resolution
379 in the **Texel** data decreases near the end of the record (see **SI9**), but this does not result in reduced age
380 model accuracy. If anything, the age of **Texel** samples is better approximated near the end of the record,
381 and age offsets are larger in the central part of the record (~30-50 mm; **Fig. 6E**). The lower accuracy in
382 the third to fifth year of the **Texel** record is likely a result of the sub-annual variability in the record that
383 is superimposed on the seasonal cycle. The lower sampling resolution later in the record mutes this
384 variability and illustrates that higher sampling resolutions do not necessarily result in better age models.
385 The constant offset of the modelled age of the **Texel** sample from the known age is a result of the way
386 the model result was aligned to start at zero for comparison with the known age (**Fig. 6F**). This was
387 done by adding the offset from zero of the modelled age of the first datapoint in the record to the entire
388 record, thereby defining an arbitrary reference point which is sensitive to the uncertainty on the age of
389 the first sample (see also **Oyster** and **Speleothem** results in **Fig. 7B-C**). Note that this alignment issue
390 does not play a role in fossil data, where model results can be aligned to growth marks in the carbonate
391 (e.g. shell growth breaks or laminae) and that it does not affect the seasonal alignment of proxy binned
392 into monthly sample bins.

393

394 **4.3 Natural carbonate records**

395 Results of modelling natural carbonate records (**Fig. 7; Table 2**; see also **SI10**) illustrate the
396 effectiveness of ShellChron on various types of records. Performance clearly depends on the resolution
397 of the record and the regularity of seasonal variability contained within. As in the virtual datasets,
398 modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ successfully mimic $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data in all records ($\overline{\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c} = 0.0$; Spearman's ρ of 0.97, 0.91
399 and 0.92 for **coral**, **oyster** and **speleothem** respectively). No consistent seasonal bias is observed in
400 $\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ and model accuracy ($p > 0.05$; see **Table 2** and **SI12**), despite significant (seasonal and inter-
401 annual) variability contained in the records (especially in **oyster** and **speleothem** records). When
402 comparing the accuracy of these records, it must be noted that the “known” age of the samples in these
403 natural carbonates is not known. Model results are instead compared with age models constructed using
404 conventional techniques such as matching $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ profiles with local temperature and/or $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ variability
405 (**oyster** and **coral** records) or even merely by linear interpolation between annual markers in the record
406 (**speleothem** record; see **Supplementary Methods**). Despite this caveat, testing results clearly show
407 that the least complicated record (**coral**; **Fig. 7A**), characterized by minimal variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and
408 growth rate and a high sampling density, has the best overall model result ($\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c = 0.0 \pm 0.14$ compared
409 to a $\sim 1.7\text{‰}$ seasonal range; $\rho = 0.97$; $\Delta t = 12 \pm 28$ d; see **Table 2**). The **oyster** record (**Fig. 7B**), which
410 has strong seasonal variability in growth rate and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{sw}$ also yields a reliable age model ($\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c = 0.0 \pm$
411 0.39 compared to a $\sim 3\text{‰}$ seasonal range; $\rho = 0.91$; $\Delta t = -15 \pm 43$ d; see **Table 2**). On closer inspection,
412 the age within the **oyster** record is clearly more difficult to model than within the **coral**, due in part to the
413 higher variability of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values superimposed on the seasonal cycle, the sharp growth cessations in
414 the winters (high $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values) and the variability in sampling resolution within the record. The latter
415 causes the first growth year of the **oyster** record to be less accurately modelled (**Fig. 7B**) while the
416 variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ causes the edges of some modelling windows to predict steep increases or decreases
417 in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ (vertical “offshoots” in modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$; **Fig. 7B**). Note that the low weighting of the edges of
418 modelling windows combined with the high overall sampling resolution in the **oyster** record minimizes
419 the effect of these “offshoots” on the accuracy of the model. The **speleothem** record (**Fig. 7C**), plagued
420 by lower sampling resolution, large inter-annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variability, restricted $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ seasonality and a lack
421 of clearly seasonal $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ forcing, yields the least reliable model result ($\Delta^{18}\text{O}_c = 0.0 \pm 0.08\text{‰}$ compared
422 to a $\sim 0.5\text{‰}$ seasonal range; $\rho = 0.92$; $\Delta t = -114 \pm 59$ d; see **Table 2**). Note that the accuracy figure
423 provided for the **speleothem** record is based on comparison with an age model relying on linear
424 interpolation between annual growth lines. This assumption of the age-distance relationship is almost

425 certainly erroneous, since drip water supply to (and therefore growth in) speleothems has been shown
426 to vary seasonally (e.g. Baldini et al., 2008), including at the very site the **speleothem** data derives from
427 (Han-sur-Lesse cave, Belgium; Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014; Vansteenberge et al., 2019). However,
428 since no reliable information is available on sub-annual variability in growth rates in this record,
429 ShellChron results cannot be validated at the sub-annual scale in this case. The high age offset (-114
430 days) in the **speleothem** model result is a consequence of the assumption in ShellChron that the highest
431 temperature (lowest $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ value) recorded in each growth year happens halfway through the year (day
432 183) and the alignment of the modelled age with the “known” age for this record (see discussion of **Texel**
433 results in 4.2). While the assumption about the phase of the temperature sinusoid is approximately valid
434 for temperature-controlled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records (see **Fig. 6** and **7**), it is problematic for speleothems, in which
435 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ is often dominated by the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ of drip water, which may not be lowest during the summer season
436 (see Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014). The timing of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ minimum can be set in the *run_model*
437 function using the *t_maxtemp* parameter. Note that changing *t_maxtemp* does not affect relative dating
438 within the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record, but, if set correctly, results in a phase shift of the age model result into better
439 alignment with the seasonal cycle.

440

441 **4.4 Modeling time**

442 The performance of both ShellChron and GRATISS in terms of computation time linearly increases
443 with the length of the record (in years; see **Fig. 8**, **Fig. S5** and **SI11**). Computation time of ShellChron
444 on the high-resolution test dataset (50 samples/yr) increases very steeply with the length of the record
445 in years (~20 minutes per additional year), while the low-resolution dataset (16 samples/yr) shows a
446 slower increase (~3 minutes per additional year; **Fig. 5A**). This contrasts with GRATISS, which
447 requires only slightly more time on high-resolution data than on low-resolution datasets (~7 and ~10
448 minutes per additional year, respectively). The difference is explained by the sliding window approach
449 applied in ShellChron, which requires more SCEUA optimization runs per year in high-resolution
450 datasets than in low resolution datasets. When plotted against the number of calculation windows or
451 samples in the dataset, running ShellChron on low-resolution and high-resolution datasets require a
452 similar increase in computation time (~0.4 minutes, or 24 seconds, per additional sample/window; **Fig.**

453 **S5)** under default SCEUA conditions. ShellChron outcompetes GRATAISS in terms of computation time
454 in datasets with fewer than ~20 samples per year, even though more SCEUA optimizations are required.

455 A key computational improvement in ShellChron is the application of a sinusoidal regression before
456 each SCEUA optimization to estimate the initial values of the modelled parameters (*sinreg* function; see
457 **equation 9** and **Fig. 1** in **Model description**). Since carbonate archives are rarely sampled for stable
458 isotope measurements above 20 samples per year (e.g. Goodwin et al., 2003; Schöne et al., 2005;
459 Lough, 2010 and references therein), the disadvantage of a steep computational increase for very high-
460 resolution archives is, in practice, a favorable tradeoff for the added control on model and measurement
461 uncertainty and smoother inter-year transitions ShellChron offers in comparison to previous models.

462 The similarity of ShellChron's accuracy in the low- and high-resolution datasets demonstrates its
463 robustness across datasets with various sampling resolutions (see also **Table 2** and **Fig. 7**).

464 Longer computation times in GRATAISS result in slightly better accuracy on the modelled age compared
465 to ShellChron on the scale of individual datapoints in low-resolution datasets (see **Fig. 8B**). However,
466 this advantage is rapidly lost when records containing multiple years are considered (**Fig. 8B**). The
467 advantage of the ShellChron model is its application of overlapping model windows, which smooth out
468 the transitions between modelled years and eliminate accumulations of model inaccuracies when
469 records grow longer. In addition, contrary to previous models, ShellChron does not rely on user-defined
470 year boundaries, which may introduce mismatches between subsequent years to be propagated
471 through the age model, even in ideal datasets such as **Case 1** (**Fig. 8B**; see also **Supplementary**
472 **Methods**). By comparison, the overall accuracy of ShellChron is much more stable within and between
473 datasets of different length, while rarely introducing offsets of more than a month. It must be noted here
474 that the cumulative, multi-year age uncertainty in the GRATAISS model (**Fig. 8B**) was calculated by
475 combining the results of consecutive growth years in the record, which the GRATAISS model models
476 separately, while avoiding age inversions and retaining the seasonal phase of the model results. This
477 procedure causes gaps in time to be introduced in the cumulative age modelled by GRATAISS
478 whenever the results of two consecutive, individually modelled growth years do not align, explaining the
479 sharp increases in age uncertainty of the GRATAISS model result (**Fig. 8B**). These cumulative
480 uncertainties are therefore not theoretically part of the model result (see year-by-year uncertainty in **Fig.**
481 **8B**) but are a necessary consequence of the way GRATAISS approximates growth years separately. If

482 only within-year inaccuracies are compared, GRATAISS results are roughly equally accurate as
483 ShellChron results (see dotted lines in **Fig. 8B**).

484 Where ShellChron considers the uncertainty on input parameters, this uncertainty is not considered in
485 most previous models (the MoGroFun model of Goodwin et al., 2003 being the exception). The added
486 uncertainty caused by input error is higher in less regular (sinusoidal) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records and in records with
487 lower sampling resolution, causing the uncertainties on GRATAISS reported here for the ideal, high-
488 resolution **Case 1** dataset to be over-optimistic. If ShellChron's model accuracy is insufficient, its
489 modular character allows the user to run the SCEUA algorithm to within more precise optimization
490 criteria by changing the model parameters (see **section 4.1**). However, this adaptation comes at a cost
491 of longer computation times.

492 The estimated uncertainty envelope (95% confidence interval) on the modelled age calculated by the
493 error propagation algorithm in ShellChron (4.7 ± 6.5 d) on average slightly underestimates the actual
494 offset between modelled age and known age in the **Case 1** record (9.3 ± 13.1 d; **Fig. 8C**). The
495 foremost difference between modelled and known uncertainty on the result is that the modelled
496 uncertainty yields a more smoothed record of uncertainty compared to the record of actual offset of the
497 model (**Fig. 8C**). ShellChron's uncertainty calculations are partly based on comparing overlapping
498 model windows, thereby smoothing out short term variations in model offset. The uncertainty of the
499 model result (both known and modelled) shows regular variability with a period of half a year (**Fig. 8C**).
500 Comparing this variability with the phase of the record (of which 6 years are plotted in **Fig. 6A**) reveals
501 that the uncertainty of the model is negatively correlated to the slope of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record. This is
502 expected, because in parts of the record with extreme values in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve, the local age model
503 result is more sensitive to small changes in the sampling distance, caused either by uncertainty in the
504 model fit or propagated uncertainty on the sampling distance defined by the user (see discussion in
505 section 4.2). The slight seasonal variability in model accuracy in **Case 1** is also shown in **Fig. 6C** and
506 comprises a difference in uncertainty of up to 10 days depending on the time of year in which the
507 datapoint is found.

508

509 **5. Applications and discussion**

510 Its new features compared to previous age model routines make ShellChron a versatile package for
511 creating age models in a range of high-resolution paleoclimate records. The discussion above
512 demonstrates that ShellChron can reconstruct the age of individual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ samples with monthly
513 precision. This level of precision is sufficient for accurate reconstructions of seasonality, defined as the
514 difference between warmest and coldest month (following USGS definitions; O'Donnell and Ignizio,
515 2012). While an improvement on this uncertainty could be of potential interest for ultra-high-resolution
516 paleoclimate studies (e.g. sub-daily variability, see Sano et al., 2012; Yan et al., 2020; de Winter et al.,
517 2020a), the increase in computation time and the sampling resolution such detailed age models demand
518 render age modelling from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records inefficient for this purpose (see **sections 4.1** and **4.4**). The
519 sampling resolution for high-resolution carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records in the literature does not typically exceed
520 100 μm due to limitations in sampling acquisition (e.g. micromilling), which even in fast-growing archives
521 limits the resolution of these records to several days at best (see Gagan et al., 1994; Van Rampelbergh
522 et al., 2014; de Winter et al., 2020c). While in some archives, high-resolution (< 100 μm) trace element
523 records could be used to capture variability beyond this limit, the monthly age resolution of ShellChron
524 is sufficient for most typical high-resolution paleoclimate studies.

525 The ability to produce uninterrupted age models from multi-year records while considering both
526 variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and uncertainties on input parameters represent major advantages of ShellChron
527 over previous age modelling solutions. As a result, ShellChron can be applied on a wide range of
528 carbonate archives (see **Fig. 7** and **Table 2**). However, testing ShellChron on different records highlights
529 the limitations of the model inherited through its underlying assumptions. The most accurate model
530 results are obtained on records with minimal growth rate and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ variability and a nearly sinusoidal
531 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record, such as tropical **coral** records (**Fig. 7A**; Gagan et al., 1994). In records where large
532 seasonal variability in growth rate and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ does occur, such as in intertidal **oyster** shells, ShellChron's
533 accuracy slightly decreases, especially near growth hiatuses in the record (see **Fig. 7B**; Ullmann et al.,
534 2010). A worst-case scenario is represented by the **speleothem** record, which not only suffers from
535 much slower and more unpredictable growth rates and contains a comparatively small annual range in
536 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$, but it responds to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ variability in drip water in the cave rather than temperature seasonality,
537 one of the assumptions underlying the current version of ShellChron (**Fig. 7C**; Vansteenbergh et al.,
538 2019). Despite these problems, ShellChron yields an age model that is remarkably accurate on an
539 annual timescale, which is as good as, or better than, the best age model that can be obtained by

540 applying layer counting on the most clearly laminated parts of the speleothem (e.g. Verheyden et al.,
541 2006). It must be noted that, while the close fit between modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ and **speleothem** $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data (ρ
542 = 0.92; $\sigma = 0.08\%$) is encouraging, a major reason for the model's success is the fact that the Proserpine
543 speleothem used in this example is known to receive significantly seasonal (though not sinusoidal) drip
544 water volumes and concentrations (Van Rampelbergh et al., 2014). Variability in drip water properties
545 and cave temperatures are known to differ strongly between cave systems (Fairchild et al., 2006;
546 Lachniet, 2009). For ShellChron (or any other $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -based age model) to work reliably in speleothem
547 records, consistent seasonal variability in either temperature or $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ should be demonstrated to
548 significantly influence the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variability in the record. In practice, these constraints make ShellChron
549 applicable in speleothems for which the cave environment varies in response to the seasonal cycle,
550 such as localities overlain by thin epikarst, well-ventilated caves or speleothems situated close to the
551 cave entrance (Verheyden et al., 2006; Feng et al., 2013; Baker et al., 2021).

552 ShellChron's ability to model multi-year records with smooth transitions between the years does not
553 compromise the accuracy of its age determination on the seasonal scale (e.g. **Fig. 6** and **7**). Many
554 paleoclimatology studies investigating the seasonal cycle rely on stacking of seasonal variability relative
555 to the annual cycle, thereby combining seasonal information from multiple years to obtain a precise
556 reconstruction of seasonal variability in the past (e.g. de Winter et al., 2018; Judd et al., 2019; Tierney
557 et al., 2020). While this can be achieved using age models of individual years (e.g. Judd et al., 2018),
558 seasonally resolved archives dated using ShellChron can also be stacked along a common seasonal
559 axis while retaining information about the multi-annual record allowing, for example, comparison
560 between consecutive years dated using the same age model including uncertainty on the age
561 determination.

562 The difficulty of applying age model routines on speleothem records highlights one of the main
563 advantages of ShellChron over pre-existing age model routines, namely its modular character. Since
564 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records from some carbonate archives, such as speleothems, cannot be described by the
565 standard combination of temperature and growth rate sinusoids on which ShellChron is based (in its
566 current version), the possibility to adapt the "building block" functions used to approximate these $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
567 records (*d18O_model*, *temperature_curve* and *growth_rate_curve*; see **Fig. 1**) while leaving the core
568 structure of ShellChron intact greatly augments the versatility of the model. The freedom to adapt the

569 building blocks used to approximate the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record theoretically enables ShellChron to model sub-
570 annual age-distance relationships in any record if the seasonal variability in the variables used to model
571 the input data are predictable and can be represented by a function. For example, since speleothem
572 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records often depend on variability in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ value of the drip water, a function describing this
573 variability through the year can replace the *temperature_curve* function to create more accurate sub-
574 annual age models for speleothems (e.g. Matthey et al., 2008; Lachniet, 2009; Van Rampelbergh et al.,
575 2014). Similarly, the *growth_rate_curve* function can be modified in case the default skewed sinusoid
576 does not accurately describe the extension rate of the record under study, and the *d18O_model* function
577 can be adapted to feature the most fitting $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -temperature or $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ - $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ relationship. Note that the
578 flexibility of this approach is limited by the expression of the annual cycle in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -
579 based dating approach in ShellChron will therefore have more trouble dating records in which the annual
580 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variability is severely dampened, such as speleothems in deeper cave systems (e.g.
581 Vansteenberge et al., 2016), or in which annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variability is not sinusoidal, such as tropical
582 records with bimodal temperature or precipitation seasonality (Knoben et al., 2018).

583 Flexibility in the definition of “building block” functions used to approximate the input data paves the way
584 for future application beyond carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records. The seasonal variability in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in some ice cores
585 can be approximated by a stable and unbiased temperature relationship (van Ommen and Morgan,
586 1997). ShellChron can therefore be modified to date sub-annual samples in these ice core records and
587 reconstruct seasonal variability in the high latitudes through the Quaternary. Similarly, inter-annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
588 variability in tree ring records are demonstrated to record variability in precipitation through the year,
589 and this variability can be modelled to improve sub-annual age models in these records (Xu et al., 2016).
590 More generally, the field of dendrochemistry has recently developed additional chemical proxies for
591 seasonality (e.g. trace element concentrations), which can be measured on smaller sample volumes
592 (and thus greater resolution) to obtain ultra-high-resolution records on which (sub-annual) dating can be
593 based (e.g. Poussart et al., 2006; Superville et al., 2017). A similar development has taken place in the
594 study of carbonate bio-archives such as corals and mollusks, of which some show strong, predictable
595 seasonal variability in trace elements (e.g. Mg/Ca and Sr/Ca ratios) which can be used to accurately
596 date these records (de Villiers et al., 1995; Sosdian et al., 2006; Durham et al., 2017; de Winter et al.,
597 2021b). Minor changes in the “building block” functions using empirical transfer functions for these trace
598 element records will enable ShellChron to capitalize on these relationships and reconstruct sub-annual

599 growth rates with improved precision due to the higher precision with which these proxies can be
600 measured compared to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records. Finally, the application of ShellChron for age model construction
601 is not necessarily limited to the seasonal cycle, as other major cycles in climate (e.g. tidal, diurnal or
602 Milankovitch cycles) leave similar marks on climate records and can thus be used as basis for age
603 modelling (e.g. Sano et al., 2012; Huyghe et al., 2019; de Winter et al., 2020a; Sinnesael et al., 2020).
604 It must be noted that, since ShellChron was developed for modeling based on annual periodicity,
605 applying it on other timescales would require more thorough adaptation of the model code than merely
606 adapting the “building block” functions to support additional proxy systems.

607 While age reconstructions are the main aim of ShellChron, the model also yields information about the
608 temperature and growth rate parameters used in each simulation window to approximate the local $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
609 curve (see *parameter matrix* in **Fig. 1** and **SI6**). These parameters hold key information about the
610 response of the archive to seasonal changes in the environment, such as the season of growth,
611 relationships between growth rate and temperature and the temperature range that is recorded.
612 Combining these parameters with records of influential environmental variables such as seawater
613 chlorophyll concentration or local precipitation patterns yields information about the response of the
614 climate archive to environmental variables, in addition to the climate or environmental change it records.
615 Study examples include the relationship between growth rate of marine calcifies and phytoplankton
616 abundance or the correlation between precipitation patterns and chemical variability in speleothems.
617 While such discussion is beyond the scope of this work, examples of parameter distributions are
618 provided in **SI5**, and the application of modelled growth rate parameters in bivalve sclerochronology is
619 discussed in more detail in Judd et al. (2018). Note that the sliding window approach of ShellChron
620 produces records of changing temperature and growth rate parameters at the scale of individual
621 samples (albeit smoothed by the sliding window approach) rather than annually, as in Judd et al. (2018).

622

623 **6. Conclusions**

624 ShellChron offers a novel, open-source solution to the problem of dating carbonate archives for high-
625 resolution paleoclimate reconstruction on a sub-annual scale. Based on critical evaluation of previous
626 age models, building on their strengths while attempting to minimize their weaknesses, ShellChron
627 provides continuous age models based on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -profiles in these archives with monthly accuracy,

628 considering the uncertainties associated with both the model itself and the input data. The monthly
629 accuracy of the model, as tested on a range of virtual and natural datasets, enables its application for
630 age determination in studies of seasonal climate and environmental variability. Higher accuracies can
631 be reached at the cost of longer computation times by adapting the model parameters, but age
632 determinations far beyond the monthly scale are unlikely to be feasible considering the limitations on
633 sampling resolution and measurement uncertainties on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ records. ShellChron's computation times
634 on datasets with sampling resolutions typical for the paleoclimatology field (up to 20 samples/yr) remain
635 practical and comparable to previous model solutions, despite adding several features that improve the
636 versatility and interpretation of model results. Its modular design allows ShellChron to be adapted to
637 different situations with comparative ease. It thereby functions as a platform for age-distance modelling
638 on a wide range of climate and environmental archives and is not limited in its application to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
639 proxy, the carbonate substrate or even to the annual cycle, as long as the relationship between the
640 proxy and the extension rate of the archive on a given time scale can be parameterized. Future
641 improvements will capitalize on this variability, expanding ShellChron beyond its current dependency on
642 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -temperature relationship in carbonates. Members of the high-resolution paleoclimate
643 community are invited to contribute to this effort by adapting the model for their purpose.

644

645 **Code availability**

646 ShellChron is worked out into a fully functioning package for the open-source computational language
647 R (version 3.5.0 or later; R Core Team, 2020). The most recent full version (v0.4.0) of the ShellChron
648 passed the code review of the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) and is freely available for
649 download as an R package on the CRAN server (see <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ShellChron>).
650 The CRAN server entry also includes detailed line-by-line documentation of the code and working
651 examples for every function. In addition, the latest development version of ShellChron is available on
652 GitHub (<https://github.com/nielsjdewinter/ShellChron>). Those interested in adapting ShellChron for their
653 research purposes are invited to do so there. Code and documentation, together with all supplementary
654 files belonging to this study, are also available on the open-source online repository Zenodo
655 (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288344>).

656

657 **Author contribution**

658 NJW designed the study, wrote the model script, carried out the test calculations and wrote the
659 manuscript.

660

661 **Competing interests**

662 There were no competing interests to declare.

663

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688

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Table 1: Overview of model parameters

Name	Description	Unit	Range
T_{av}	Average temperature	°C	Variable, generally between 0°C–30°C
T_{amp}	Temperature range (2*amplitude)	°C	Variable, generally <20°C
T_{pha}	Phase of temperature sinusoid	d	0–365 days
T_{per}	Period of temperature sinusoid	d	365 days by default
G_{av}	Average growth rate	µm/d	Variable, generally between 0–100 µm/day
G_{amp}	Range of growth rates	µm/d	Variable, generally <200 µm/day
G_{pha}	Phase of growth rate sinusoid	d	0–365 days
G_{per}	Period of growth rate sinusoid	d	365 days by default
G_{skw}	Skewness factor of GR sinusoid	-	0–100, with 50 meaning no skew
D	Distance along the record	µm	Depends on archive
t	Age	d	Depends on archive
L_{win}	Length of sampling window	#	Depends on sampling resolution
w	Weighting factor on sample	-	0–1
i	Position relative to model window	-	0– L_i
I	Intercept of sinusoid (T_{av} or G_{av})	°C or µm/d	
A	Amplitude of sinusoid $\left(\frac{T_{amp}}{2} \text{ or } \frac{G_{amp}}{2}\right)$	°C or µm/d	
P	Period of sinusoid (T_{per} or G_{per})	d	
ϕ	Phase of sinusoid (T_{pha} or G_{pha})	d	

937

938

Table 2: Overview of datasets and model results

Dataset	Resolution	Length	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ seasonal range	Complications
Test case	7-12 yr ⁻¹	5 yr	~5‰	Variable $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, Variable GR
Case 1	50 yr ⁻¹	6 yr	~4.3‰	None
Texel	26–45 yr ⁻¹	10 yr	~4‰	Variable $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, Variable GR
Coral	30–49 yr ⁻¹	6 yr	~1.7‰	Variable GR
Oyster	23–45 yr ⁻¹	3.5 yr	~3‰	Variable $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, Variable GR
Speleothem	4–13 yr ⁻¹	14 yr	~0.5‰	Variable $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, Variable GR, Non-sinusoidal $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ -forcing

Dataset	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ offset ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Age offset ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Spearman's ρ	Observations
Test case	0.0 \pm 0.49 ‰	7 \pm 32 d	0.94	Slightly out of phase
Case 1	0.0 \pm 0.27‰	4 \pm 12 d	0.98	-
Texel	0.0 \pm 0.41‰	30 \pm 24 d	0.92	-
Coral	0.0 \pm 0.14‰	12 \pm 28 d	0.97	-
Oyster	0.0 \pm 0.39‰	-15 \pm 43 d	0.91	Reduced accuracy near growth stops
Speleothem	0.0 \pm 0.08‰	-114 \pm 59 d	0.92	Susceptible to phase offsets; Only reliable on inter-annual scale

939

940

941 **Figure 1:** Schematic overview of ShellChron. Names in *italics* refer to functions (encapsulated in
942 rounded rectangular boxes) and operations within functions. Rectangular boxes represent data. Arrows
943 represent the flow of information between model components. Note that some operations are
944 encapsulated in functions (e.g. *Error propagation* in *export results*) and that some functions are only
945 used within other functions (e.g. *peakid* in *cumulative_day*). All data structures outside *wrap_function*
946 represent input and output of the model. Detailed documentation of all functions and operations in
947 ShellChron is provided in **SI1** (see also **Code availability**).

948

949 **Figure 2: A)** Plots of the growth rate (light green), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ (blue) and temperature (red) records (in time
950 domain) from which the **Test case** was produced. Black triangles on the bottom of the temperature plot
951 indicate the ages of the samples taken from the record. **B)** The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record for the **Test Case** generated
952 after equidistant sampling using the *seasonalclumped* package (de Winter et al., 2021a) with a sampling
953 interval of 0.5 mm. Error bars on sampling distance (0.1 mm) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ (0.1‰) fall within the symbols.
954 Vertical grey dashed lines indicate user-provided year markers and the blue bar on top of this plot shows
955 an example of the width of a modelling window. See **Supplementary Methods** for details on producing
956 the **Test case** $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ record and **SI3** for the R script used to generate the data.

957

958 **Figure 3:** Schematic overview of the structure of the result array in which ShellChron stores the raw
959 results of each model window. Data is stored in three dimensions: The sample number (rows in the
960 figure), the window number (columns in the figure) and the number of modelled parameters
961 (represented by the stacked table “sheets” in the figure). Note that the first 5 columns of each “sheet”
962 represent the user-provided input data (see example in **SI2**), and that the model result data starts from
963 column 6. The window length is determined by the user-provided indication of year transitions (column
964 3). Rows of dots in the figure are placeholders for (input or result) values. Shading of these dots in the
965 window columns indicate differential weighting of modelled values in function of their location relative
966 to the sliding window. The horizontal box shows how these weighting factors within each sample
967 window (in vertical direction) result in weighting of different estimates of modelled parameters for the
968 same data point (in horizontal direction). Shading of input data and window number towards the
969 bottom and right edge of the figure, respectively, indicates that the number of input values (and thus

970 simulation windows) is only limited to the length of the input table and may therefore continue
971 indefinitely (at the expense of longer computation times, see **Fig. 8** in **Model performance**).

972

973 **Figure 4:** Showing the steps taken to simulate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data in the *run_model* function on the **Test case**.

974 **A)** Temperature sinusoid used to approximate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data in the first modelling window (see **D**),
975 produced using a combination of *temperature_curve* and *d18O_model* functions. Symbols indicate the
976 positions of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ samples on the temperature curve, with estimated $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values shown on the
977 secondary axis (right). **B)** Skewed growth rate sinusoid fit to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data using the
978 *growth_rate_curve* function. Note the shift towards steeper growth rate increase around the 300th
979 model day (autumn season in this example). See **Fig. S2** for a detailed description of the growth rate
980 sinusoid. **C)** The modelled age-distance relationship for this window after fitting $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ data, resulting
981 from aligning the estimated age of samples (x-axes on **A**) with the distance in sampling direction (x-
982 axis in **D**) using the cumulative growth rate function (**B**). **D)** $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ profile of the **Test case** (green) with
983 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curve of the first modelling window (red), which results from the combination of temperature
984 (**A**) and growth rate (**B**) sinusoids, plotted on top (*growth_model* function). **E)** Result after simulating
985 the full $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ profile of the **Test case** (green) using *run_model*, with the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curves of individual
986 modelling windows shown in red.

987

988 **Figure 5:** Result of testing ShellChron with various combinations of SCEUA parameters and
989 sinusoidal regression on the **Test case** dataset (see **Fig. 2**). The leftmost plots illustrate performance
990 of ShellChron under default SCEUA parameters. Plots to the right show various combinations of
991 parameters that deviate from the default (see labels on top and bottom of plot) **A)** Fits of the model
992 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ curves (red) with the data (black). **B)** Violin plots showing the distribution of modelled $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$
993 offset from the data. **C)** Age-distance plots showing modelled (red) and known (black) age-depth
994 relationships for each scenario. **D)** Violin plots showing the distribution of age offsets from the known
995 age-depth relationship. SD = standard deviation, N = number of datapoints, sinres = sinusoidal
996 regression, maxn, ngs, kstop, peeps and pcento are SCEUA parameters (see Duan et al., 1992 and
997 explanation in **section 4.1**). Data on test results is provided in **SI11**.

998

999 **Figure 6:** Result of applying ShellChron on two virtual datasets: **Case 1** (top, see **SI8**) and **Texel**,
1000 (bottom, see **SI9**). Leftmost panels (**A** and **D**) show the model fit of individual sample windows (red) on
1001 the data (black, including horizontal and vertical error bars), with in the top left Spearman's correlation
1002 coefficients (ρ) and standard deviations on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ estimate (σ_{est}). Middle panels (**B** and **E**) show the
1003 resulting age model (red, including shaded 95% confidence level) compared with the known age-
1004 distance relationship of both records. Histograms in the top left of age-distance plots show the offset
1005 between modelled and measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ (as visualized in panels **A** and **D**) with standard deviations of
1006 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ offset (σ_{off}) and offset averages (μ). Histograms in the bottom right of age-distance plots show
1007 the offset between modelled and known ages (in days) of each datapoint, including standard deviations
1008 on the age accuracy (σ_{acc}) and mean age offset (μ). Rightmost panels (**C** and **F**) highlight age offsets
1009 binned in 12 monthly time bins based on their position relative to the annual cycle to illustrate how
1010 accuracy varies over the seasons. Grey envelopes indicate 95% confidence levels on the monthly age
1011 offset within these monthly time bins. The horizontal red dashed line indicates no offset (modelled age
1012 is equal to the known age of the sample).

1013

1014 **Figure 7:** Overview of model results for the three test datasets from real carbonate archives: **(A) coral**,
1015 **(B) oyster** and **(C) speleothem**. Lower panels indicate the fit of individual model windows (in red) with
1016 the data (in black) while upper panels show the age model (in red) compared to the "true" age-distance
1017 relationship with histograms showing model accuracy (in days, top left) and model fit ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ offset in ‰,
1018 bottom right). Color scheme follows **Figure 3**. Note that the true age-distance relationship is not known
1019 for these natural records, but is estimated using known growth seasonality (**coral**), comparison with *in*
1020 *situ* temperature and salinity measurements (**oyster**) or simply by interpolating between annual growth
1021 lines (**speleothem**). See **Supplementary Methods** for details and **SI10** for raw data.

1022

1023 **Figure 8:** Overview of the result of timing ShellChron and the GRATISS model on the same datasets
1024 **(A)**, comparing the accuracies of both models **(B)** and comparing the accuracy as calculated by
1025 ShellChron with the known offset in the age model **(C)**. In **(A)** and **(B)**, low resolution datasets are

1026 plotted in dark blue (ShellChron) and dark green (GRATAISS), while high-resolution datasets plot in
1027 light blue (ShellChron) and light green (GRATAISS). Solid lines represent ShellChron and dashed
1028 lines show performance of the GRATAISS model. Green dotted lines in **(B)** show the accuracies of the
1029 GRATAISS model on a year-by-year basis (without accumulating error due to linking consecutive
1030 years) The black box in **(A)** and **(B)** highlights the dataset used in **(C)**. In **(C)**, dark blue lines, bars and
1031 boxplot indicate true offset of the model from the actual sample age, while light blue lines, bars and
1032 boxplot show the accuracy of the model as calculated from the propagated errors on model and input
1033 data. Raw data is provided in **SI11**.